

The Role of Powerful Radio Jets in the Host Galaxy of a Quasar in the First Gyr of the Universe

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High-redshift quasars can shed light on the co-evolution of central supermassive black holes and their host galaxies in the very early Universe. This can be tested by studying the first quasars within 1 Gyr after the Big Bang (or at redshift $z > 6$) emerging during the Epoch of Reionization [1]. Multiple studies searching for quasars during this epoch have shown a population of > 300 quasars with supermassive black hole masses ranging from $10^8 - 10^9 M_\odot$ (e.g., [2, 3]). However, only 10% of these quasars are bright at radio wavelengths [4]. The radio-loudness depends on the ratio of the brightness of the source at rest-frame optical and radio emission using the following definitions $R_{4400} = f_{\nu, 5 \text{ GHz}} / f_{\nu, 4400} > 10$ [5] or $R_{2500} = f_{\nu, 5 \text{ GHz}} / f_{\nu, 2500 \text{ \AA}} > 10$ [6]. In order to understand why the high-redshift radio-loud population fraction is much lower, it is necessary to make comparative studies with the radio-quiet population. The following research presents the first attempt at investigating the host galaxies of a radio-loud quasar in the rest-frame Far-Infrared and observe whether there are indications of the jet affecting the cold dust from the galaxy [see also 7].

We investigate quasar P352–15 near the end of Reionization at $z = 5.832 \pm 0.001$ and one of the most powerful radio sources with $R_{4400} \& R_{2500} > 1,000$ [8]. High-resolution VLBA imaging of the quasar (Figure 1) reveals radio hot spots indicating evidence of a kpc-scale radio jet (~ 1.6 kpc) at this high redshift [9]. This makes P352–15 the ideal laboratory to study for the first time the influence of jets in the host galaxy and also the timescales for black hole accretion and jet launch.

Figure 1: VLBA high-resolution image of P352–15. The black cross is centered at the quasar optical position: R.A. (J2000) = $23^{\text{h}}29^{\text{m}}36^{\text{s}}.8363$, DEC. (J2000) = $-15^{\circ}20'14''.460$. The extent among the hot spots is $0''.3$, corresponding to 1.62 kpc at $z = 5.83$. Figure adapted (See [9]).

The SED in rest-frame FIR and Radio Emission

We study the spectral energy distribution of this quasar at millimeter (far-infrared in the rest-frame) and radio observations. The millimeter continuum emission for radio-quiet quasars at these redshifts has usually been interpreted as cold dust and is modeled as a modified black body (MBB) [10]. This model depends on the temperature of the cold dust (T) and an emissivity spectral index (β) that describes e.g. the size of dust grains. Typical values in the literature of radio-quiet quasars assume $T = 30 \text{ K} - 100 \text{ K}$, and $\beta = 1.6$ or 1.95 (e.g., [11, 12]). We use two mm-continuum measurements of P352–15 from ALMA 290 GHz and NOEMA 100 GHz observations to fit the MBB. However, the analysis shows that it is not possible to model these millimeter measurements as cold dust alone, see Figure 2. The emission at 100 GHz is an order of magnitude higher than the one predicted by any of the MBB models. Therefore at this frequency we are observing emission from another source, the next suspect being synchrotron emission.

The radio emission observed in the SED is produced by the jets, more specifically by synchrotron emission generated from relativistic electrons spiralling around the magnetic field produced from the accreting black hole. The synchrotron radiation is well described as a simple power law of the form $S_\nu \propto \nu^\alpha$, where S_ν is the observed flux density at the frequency ν and α is the radio spectral index. P352–15 has radio observations with GMRT at 215 MHz, and with the VLA at 1.4 GHz and 3 GHz. Using these measurements it is possible to calculate spectral index $\alpha_3^{0.215} = -0.88$. However, when extrapolating this slope to the millimeter measurements, the synchrotron emission at 100 GHz is about three times brighter than the observed with NOEMA (Figure 2). This suggests evidence of the strong synchrotron emission in P352–15 affecting the dust-dominated continuum emission. Furthermore, this implies a break in the synchrotron spectrum.

Timescale for Jet Aging

Finding the frequency at which the power-law from synchrotron emission breaks is crucial to calculate spectral aging of the jet. This steepening occurs because the higher energy electrons lose energy faster ($rate \propto E^2$) and as they cool down from recent re-acceleration in the jet caused by shocks, this steepening effect is seen at the higher frequencies (see yellow arrows in Figure 2). Synchrotron aging t_{syn} thus depends on the magnetic field strength B and frequency break ν_b [13]. For the case of P352–15, the analysis of high-resolution VLBA observations presents a powerful magnetic field of $B \sim 3.5 \text{ mG}$

Figure 2: Spectral energy distribution (SED) of P352–15, adapted from [8]. The millimeter ALMA and NOEMA measurements are inconsistent with a MBB modeled at different dust temperatures and dust emissivity spectral indexes. The radio data at 215 MHz–3 GHz are well described by synchrotron emission. However, extrapolating that power law (dashed line) would be inconsistent with the millimeter data. To explain this SED, the synchrotron emission must steepen or break at high frequencies as denoted by the yellow arrows.

[9]. The missing ingredient is the frequency break ν_b , for which we have performed VLA observations (PI: Rojas-Ruiz) in all available bands from 1.5 GHz – 45 GHz and are currently under analysis.

Timescale for Black Hole Accretion

The surrounding neutral intergalactic medium (IGM) of a quasar in the Epoch of Reionization begins to be ionized by UV radiation produced from the supermassive black hole (SMBH) accretion. It is therefore possible to calculate the timescale for quasar activity t_Q by measuring the size of the ionizing bubble (e.g., [14, 15]). A bigger bubble implies that the SMBH has been accreting for longer time and there is more flux transmission blueward of the Ly- α . We are analyzing available X-Shooter spectra of P352–15 covering the rest-frame UV/Optical emission showing this flux enhancement. Therefore, we will be able to constrain t_Q and compare this timescale to that of the jet from synchrotron aging t_{syn} . We would thus be able to discern among the possible scenarios presented in Figure 3 where a) the jet is launched soon after the SMBH turns on, b) the jet takes a longer time to form after the SMBH begins accreting, or c) the SMBH has intermittent accretion allowing time for IGM recombination but the jet from earlier activity is still present.

The future timescale studies of P352–15 will be a pioneering work on understanding better the black hole – host galaxy formation and jet ejection mechanisms for quasars within the first Gyr of the Universe.

Figure 3: Scenarios of the possible comparison timescales between black hole accretion (black circle) determined by t_Q (orange bubble growth) and jet launch t_{syn} (purple jet growth).

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